

DEVELOP THE ABILITY TO USE COMMUNICATION TOOLS IN A VARIETY OF SITUATIONS IN SPEECH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES

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ANNOTATION: *This article provides information on speech development processes and methods of using developmental tools in preschool children.*

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Speech development methodology is the study of the laws of pedagogical activity aimed at the development of speech in preschool children. The approach to the problem of speech development is based on the fundamental general psychological research of educators, psychologists and methodologists (L.S. Vgotsky, LA Wenger, P.Ya. Galperin, V.V.Davdov, A.V.Zaporojes, N.N.Poddyakov, A.P.Usova, Ye.A.Flerina, etc.). positions. These studies do not treat teaching and development equally, but at the same time emphasize that education has a leading role in helping children develop tools and methods to find their way in a being that creates a 'close development zone' (L.S. Vgotsky). The problem of speech teaching has always been and will remain one of the leading problems of preschool didactics. The role of teaching in the development of the child's native language has been repeatedly discussed by thinkers of the East (Ibn Sino, Alisher Navoi, etc.) and the West (YA Comenius, etc.), as well as K.D. Ushinsky, Ye.I. Tikheeva , Noted by A.P.Usova, L.A.Penevskaya. Ibn Sina taught the children to talk calmly and without touching his person without shouting, and to start the conversation with stories and legends.

A. Navoi expressed words, speech and their importance in human life in a highly artistic way through images. Based on the idea of comprehensive development of natural abilities, YA Comenius set tasks from an early age to teach children to know, to move, to speak. He believed that the same care should be taken to develop "mind and speech." Because the child expresses his thoughts through speech and interacts with the people around him, by mastering the speech he understands the world around him, and as a result of communication with other children the child develops speech and thinking.

K.D. Ushinsky put forward the thesis that in the first education the teaching of the mother tongue "constitutes the main, central subject". According to him, "a child may not be able to master this great heritage for a long time, but never - he will not be able to truly make it his own spiritual wealth."

E.I. Tikheeva was the first of K.D. Ushinsky's followers to use the term "language teaching" in relation to preschool age. In his opinion, the basis of the system of educational work in kindergarten should be the regular teaching of the native language from the first age, which he considered one of the main tasks of the preschool.

Ye.A. Flerina has also made a significant contribution to solving the problem of mother tongue teaching. He used the term "teaching" in a broad sense to describe the pedagogical influence of adults on children. Based on this understanding of education, he identified three forms: teaching in the child's daily life, during his various activities; voluntary group activities; compulsory activities in which "one or another educational task is assigned to the whole group".

E.A. Flerina warned about the dangers of "narrowly solving the problem of preschool education", emphasizing the specificity of teaching preschool children: and through tutoring and tutoring in tutoring and special classes. " In her educational system, she has focused on the arts and their use in a variety of activities, including art and speech, to develop children's abilities. Research on the problem of teaching speech to preschool children continues in accordance with the above guidelines.

Analysis of psychological and pedagogical research in the field of speech development of preschool children and teaching them their mother tongue allows us to draw the following conclusions speech development is a very complex and multifaceted process in which a child acquires a socio-historical experience that is central to his or her individual development. factor process.

It is not a spontaneous process, but a creative process that offers pedagogical guidance. The educator who manages the child's speech development process knows the laws, mechanisms and features of this process at different ages, is able to see the individual characteristics of speech development and the most effective way to influence the child's speech, taking into account the specific characteristics of the child.

An analysis of the phenomenon of "child speech development" itself and the process of its management leads to the conclusion that educators need special training to work in the field of speech development in preschool children. The ability of an early childhood and preschool educator to teach children their mother tongue is an important indicator of his or her professional training. All

the mental abilities that a child is endowed with by nature emerge and develop through the acquisition of the mother tongue, especially through its preschool learning. The extent to which children inherit the spiritual riches of the people passed down from generation to generation in their mother tongue, the ability of pupils to master the scientific achievements of their time in the future, their commitment to the advanced poetic and aesthetic ideals of humanity their ability to be full builders of society depends on the educator.

In order to teach children their mother tongue, the future educator must study in depth the theory of speech development methods and master the methods known in science in this field, understand the laws of the child's mother tongue. Methods of teaching the native language is a branch of pedagogical science. It includes methods of speech development in preschool education and methods of teaching Uzbek (Russian) in primary and secondary schools. Each has its own purpose, mission, and content.

Speech development methodology is the study of the laws of pedagogical activity aimed at the development of speech in preschool children. The main task of the methodology is to develop the most effective tools, methods and techniques of speech development on a scientific and pedagogical basis, as well as to equip kindergarten teachers with them to successfully develop the necessary speaking skills in children. The main purpose of the method of speech development is to develop in children the skills of oral communication, its communication with others. The methodology of speech development allows you to find answers to the following key questions: what to teach (what speech skills to develop in children), how to teach (under what conditions should be used in the formation of children's speech, what methods and techniques should be used), why exactly how to teach (what methods of speech development are based on what data from theory and practice).

The theory of speech development methodology reflects the objective features of teaching children their native language, summarizes all the positive results in the field of speech development methodology, created and currently in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad. The theory of speech development methodology is developing along with methodological practice. The viability of some methodological rules is being tested in practice, and the practice itself poses important issues to science that have not yet been resolved. An educator who does not know methodological theory blindly educates children only on the basis of their own assumptions or by copying the experiences of others. He misses a lot because he doesn't know the colorful methods and techniques.

Speech development techniques are inextricably linked to other special methods in preschool education, as speech is one of the most important tools for the full development of a child's personality. Understanding the speech of

others and the child's own active speech are necessary in any pedagogical process. Speech accompanies a child's whole activity.

According to EI Tikheeva: "The mother tongue, its unimpeded and comprehensive development should be the basis of education." Timely mastery of speech is the most important and the first condition for the development of a child's full psyche and its subsequent proper development. Timely means that the lessons begin in the first days after the birth of the child, and complete means that the language material is sufficient and encourages the child to master speech at every age, using its full potential.

It is also important to pay attention to the development of a child's speech in the early stages, because during this period the child's brain grows rapidly and its functions are formed. Physiologists know that the functions of the central nervous system can be easily exercised during their natural formation. Without exercise, the development of these tasks slows down and may even stop altogether.

“Such a ‘decisive’ period of speech development is the first three years of a child’s life: by this time the anatomical development of the speech areas of the brain is largely complete, the child learns the basic grammatical forms of the mother tongue, a large vocabulary is formed. If a child's speech is not given enough attention in the first three years, he or she will have to work hard to make up for it in the future.”

The methodology of speech development, like any other pedagogical discipline, belongs to the social sciences. The teachings of language and thought are its methodological basis.

Just like language, the thinking that emerges and develops during a person's co-operative activity is a reflection of the being that surrounds him. The strong organic connection of language with thinking is due to the need for people to be productive, to exchange ideas, and to act together. Although language and thought cannot exist without each other, they do not belong to the same phenomenon. Thinking is the opposite of being an object, and language is a way of expressing, reinforcing, and conveying an idea to others. Words and concepts are dialectically interrelated.

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